

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt using 4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol and Tetrabutylammonium Perchlorate

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The thiocyanate and *o*-nitrocresol¹ methods are used extensively for colorimetric determination of cobalt, but these methods are less selective and have several disadvantages. A colorimetric method for determination of cobalt with 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR) was recommended by Pollard *et al.*². The use of PAR and tetrabutylammonium (TBA) perchlorate for determination of osmium has been reported³. In the present investigation, a simple and rapid extractive spectrophotometric method for determination of cobalt using PAR and TBA in acidic medium is described.

Results and Discussion

A quantitative extraction of Co^{II} (0.1–2.5 ppm) was obtained when the concentration range of the three, viz. PAR, TBA and HCl were in the range 10⁻⁴–10⁻² M. In this composite system, any of the reagents with concentration lower than 10⁻⁴ M would lower absorbance value at 515 nm and higher than 10⁻² M caused excess deepening of the colour. A concentration of 10⁻³ M PAR was found to be adequate for Co^{II}-PAR-TAB system.

Various solvents like dichloromethane, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, methyl isobutyl ketone, isobutanol and n-butanol were tested for the extraction of Co^{II}-PAR-TBA system. A quantitative extraction of cobalt by shaking the mixture for 30 s was achieved by using n-butanol. The complex remained stable for more than 1 h. Beer's law was obeyed for 0.1–2.5 ppm of cobalt in the final solution. Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity were found to be 0.0016 µg cm⁻² and 3.587 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ respectively, at 515 nm.

The effect of diverse ions in the determination of cobalt(II) (amount used 10 µg) was studied. The tolerance limit (µg) was set at the amount required to cause less than 3% error in the recovery of cobalt: Ag^I, Mo^{VI}, fluoride, chloride, thiourea (1000); citrate, tartrate (700); oxalate, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II} (550); Cd^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, W^{VI}, U^{VI}, Sn^{II}, Pb^{II}, bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, thiocyanate (500); Au^{III} (250); phosphate (150); Fe^{II} (after separation with 6 M HCl and MIBK), Ni^{II} (after separation with DMG and chloroform), V^V (using ascorbic acid as masking agent), Hg^{II} (100); Pt^{VI}, Pd^{II} (50). EDTA interfered.

The method was applied for determination of cobalt in synthetic mixtures and the results (average of 5 determinations) are shown in Table 1.

TABLE-I ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Composition (µg)	Co ^{II} found (µg)
1.	Co ^{II} (10), Ag ^I (500), Pt ^{VI} (50)	9.92
2.	Co ^{II} (10), Zn ^{II} (100), Ni ^{II} (100) ^a	9.90
3.	Co ^{II} (10), Cd ^{II} (100), Fe ^{II} (100) ^b	9.88
4.	Co ^{II} (10), Mo ^{VI} (100), U ^{VI} (100)	9.94

^aAfter separation with DMG. ^bAfter separation with 6 M HCl MIBK.

Results of 10 estimations with 4 µg of Co^{II} showed that standard deviation and coefficient of variation were 0.0027 and 1.11% respectively.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-3210 spectrophotometer was used.

A stock solution of Co^{II} was prepared from cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate (B.D.H.) and solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by appropriate dilution. Solutions of PAR (in distilled water) and TBA (in ethanol) were prepared. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from chloride, nitrate or sulphate (in case cations) and sodium, potassium or ammonium (in case anions) salts.

Procedure: To an aliquot of cobalt(II) solution containing 1–25 µg of Co^{II}, PAR solution (1 ml) was added and then made upto 10 ml with 1 × 10⁻³ M HCl. To it TBA (1 ml) and n-butanol (10 ml) were added. The resulting mixture was gently shaken for 30 s and the organic layer was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance of the organic extract was measured at 515 nm against the reagent blank.

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